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Challenging situations and protective factors of dyslexia from the perspective of students, parents, and dyslexia or speech-language therapists in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland: when I read something, I simply don't understand anything

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explores the challenging school-related situations and protective factors for students with dyslexia from the perspectives of students, parents, and dyslexia or speech-language therapists across Germany, Austria, and Switzerland. Utilising a participatory approach, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 22 students aged between eight years 11 months and 11 years nine months, and insights gathered from their parents and therapists through questionnaires. The findings suggest convergences in the experiences of stressors, such as negative classroom interactions, time pressure during tasks, and emotional distress, highlighting the multifaceted nature of dyslexia. Notably, while students reported feelings of discomfort and frustration, self-esteem issues were more frequently articulated by parents and therapists, suggesting a gap in students' self-awareness of their emotional challenges. The current study underscores the importance of adopting a multiperspective framework to understand the interplay between cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions of dyslexia. By integrating insights from various stakeholders, the paper aims to inform the development of tailored interventions that address both academic and psychosocial needs, fostering a supportive environment for students with dyslexia. This research contributes to a more ecological understanding of dyslexia, emphasising the necessity for collaborative support systems in educational settings.

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Introduction

Developmental dyslexia is a neurodevelopmental disorder that affects around 7% of individuals (Yang et al., 2022). However, prevalence rates vary widely depending on the definitions (for example, subskills, operational descriptions) employed. It can be categorised into difficulties in either reading (reduced reading fluency, reading accuracy, and reading comprehension), writing/spelling (difficulties in spelling accuracy, grammar and punctuation accuracy), or both, that cannot be explained by general intellectual difficulties or a lack of instruction (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2022). It has to be noted as a limitation of the ICD-11 (WHO, 2022) that it requires a discrepancy between reading/spelling skills and cognitive skills, which can complicate diagnostic process (Schulte-Körne, 2021). In contrast, this discrepancy criterion is not included in the DSM-5 (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Additionally, it has been criticised that obtaining support depends on first receiving a diagnostic label. While dyslexia has an obvious impact on students' academic performance, there is a large variety of effects in other areas of development, such as self-esteem, self-concept, emotional distress, and social ostracising (Livingston et al., 2018). Accordingly, children with dyslexia are at elevated risk for academic underachievement, emotional strain, and long-term educational disadvantage (for example, Esser et al., 2002).

Support systems to address these academic difficulties are in place in all German-speaking countries. In Austria and Germany, dyslexia or learning therapists are academically trained to work with clients with dyslexia and therapy typically takes place outside regular classroom instruction after school. Their focus is mainly on addressing students' difficulties in reading and writing/spelling, while usually also incorporating measures to help build up students' self-image and reduce negative emotions related to learning (Bender et al., 2017). Evidence-based interventions should be tailored to the specific symptom profiles of each student, addressing their individual areas of difficulty in reading and/or spelling (Galuschka & Schulte-Körne, 2015). In Switzerland, this role falls mostly to speech therapists and/or special education teachers. While ideally these specialists work together with teachers, parents, and each other within a multi-professional team, this is not always the case. School systems often lack support structures or procedures that combine all the available resources and consider all the different environments and social circles a student encounters in their everyday life.

Including environmental and social aspects in the support of students with dyslexia could be beneficial for them. Many ethological models of dyslexia consider not only medical and biological aspects, which are reflected in specific patterns of brain activity (for example, Goswami, 2008), but also psychological and social factors that contribute to the emergence of dyslexia and can either reduce or exacerbate the difficulties encountered during the acquisition of reading and writing/spelling skills (for example, Macdonald, 2019).

Indeed, students who are diagnosed with dyslexia often report psychological or mental issues in conjunction with their academic challenges. In their review, Livingston et al. (2018) give an extensive overview of the most frequently reported secondary consequences in persons with dyslexia. They found that, specifically, reduced emotional well-being is discussed frequently in studies on dyslexia, and that this is often related to other secondary consequences, including lower self-esteem, problems in social relationships,

and behavioural issues. For example, with regard to emotional consequences, simply being diagnosed with dyslexia may elicit complex emotions. There can be relief over the knowledge that their difficulties have an explanation, but also persistent negative emotions about the limitations that are not likely to ever fully disappear (Deacon et al., 2020; Gibson & Kendall, 2010). Regarding social consequences, certain learning arrangements may lead to stigmatisation within the classroom and can further negatively impact emotional well-being. For example, being asked to read aloud in front of the entire class is often associated with anxiety and may increase the risk of being ridiculed (McNulty, 2003; Skaalvik, 2004). Outside the classroom, doing homework with or without their parents is a particularly stressful experience for both students with dyslexia and their parents (Leitão et al., 2017; Rowan, 2010; Xiao et al., 2022).

To summarise, students with dyslexia may face many challenges in and out of the classroom that are not only academic, but also psycho-social in nature. While prior studies have contributed considerably to the understanding of students' perspectives, less is known about how these views align or diverge from those of parents and therapists. It is therefore necessary to gain a deeper insight into these perspectives in order to develop a more holistic and context-sensitive account of dyslexia.

The current study

The current study aims to identify and compare challenging situations and protective factors for students with dyslexia from the perspective of students, dyslexia therapists and speech therapists, as well as parents/guardians. It aims to answer the following research question: *Which situations in the school environment do students with dyslexia or reading/spelling difficulties, their parents, and professionals consider to be stressful or protective?* This multi-perspective approach should help tailor interventions more precisely to students with dyslexia, taking into account multiple perspectives and settings.

Methodology

This qualitative study, conducted as part of the Lubo-LRS project (University of Cologne, 2025), explored challenging school-related situations and protective factors for students with dyslexia. In order to record how different school situations are perceived by persons involved, the perspectives of students, parents and professionals were surveyed using a participatory approach. In each country, dyslexia therapists (Austria and Germany) or speech therapists (Switzerland) were contacted to identify children with dyslexia or reading/spelling difficulties in Grades 2 to 5, aged between eight years 11 months and 11 years nine months, currently receiving therapy and who might be eligible and willing to participate in this study. All children for whom parental consent to participate was obtained were included in the sample. The students' perspectives were obtained through semi-structured interviews (see Appendix A for interview schedule sample) conducted by the therapists. These interviews focused on challenges encountered during the school day (for example, academic tasks, interactions with teachers and peers) as well as on after-school experiences and activities.

In addition, therapists and parents/guardians completed a short questionnaire assessing their perceptions of school-related stressors and protective factors for the student.

The questionnaire included the following question: “Which school situations do you find particularly stressful for your child based on your own observations, statements from the child or statements from teachers (situations with school tasks, with teachers, with other children and/or other school situations)?” The therapists also provided background information on each student, including gender, age, school grade, current school year, start of dyslexia therapy, diagnosis related to reading and writing, time of diagnosis, and any additional diagnoses.

Research perspective

The study is informed by an ecological view that understands dyslexia as rooted in neurodevelopmental differences whose impact is shaped by interactions across home, school, and therapy contexts (Rosa & Tudge, 2013). The researchers applied a qualitative, interpretive framework which assumes that “challenging situations” and “protective factors” are best understood through how students, parents, and professionals describe and make sense of their experiences (Mayring, 2015). Accordingly, semi-structured interviews and open questions were chosen to allow participants to articulate their perspectives in their own words rather than within predefined categories.

Ethical considerations

Written informed consent for participation in this study was obtained from the participants’ legal guardians/next of kin. Participation was voluntary, and participants could withdraw from the study at any time without negative consequences. The study was conducted in accordance with institutional and national ethical guidelines in all three countries, and all data were pseudonymised before analysis.

All procedures performed in the study complied with the ethical principles for medical research involving human participants of the 1964 WMA Declaration of Helsinki and its subsequent amendments, and were approved by Regional School Board for Styria (Bildungsdirektion Steiermark).

Sample

Students

Interviews were conducted by nine different dyslexia or speech-language therapists with a total of 22 student participants (11 males) in Germany ($n = 8$), Austria ($n = 5$), and Switzerland ($n = 9$) between December 2021 and March 2022. The students were between eight years 11 months and 11 years nine months old ($M = 10.14$, $SD = 0.89$). At the time of the interviews, the students were attending the second ($n = 1$), third ($n = 4$), fourth ($n = 16$), or fifth ($n = 1$) grade. Some students ($n = 10$) had repeated a grade and thus had accumulated more years of schooling.

For four students, reading/writing difficulties were identified using standardised tests without a formal psychological diagnosis, one had a specific reading disorder, while the other 17 students had a diagnosis prior to this study. Most students ($n = 13$) had a diagnosis of dyslexia based on the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (10th Revision; ICD-10, F81.0). Additional diagnoses

included mixed disorders of scholastic skills (F81.3, $n = 3$), isolated reading disorder (not classifiable under ICD-10, $n = 1$), and isolated spelling disorder (F81.1, $n = 1$). Comorbid diagnoses were reported for 11 students, some with multiple conditions. The most frequent were dyscalculia ($n = 7$), developmental language disorder (DLD; $n = 5$), and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD; $n = 3$). Detailed sample characteristics are presented in [Appendix B](#).

Therapists and parents/guardians

Sixteen parent questionnaires were completed (one per family), and 22 questionnaires were filled out by dyslexia therapists or speech-language therapists, each matched to the respective student.

Data analysis

The data were analysed using qualitative content analysis (Kuckartz, 2018; Mayring, 2015) with MAXQDA 2024 (VERBI Software [VERBI], 2021). Coding was performed using a category system developed specifically for this study by two independent coders (Cohen's Kappa = .97). The category system consists of four main categories: (1) negative interactions (with parents, classmates/in class, teachers); (2) task mastery (working speed, pressure of grades, additional support, homework, writing, reading/verbal expression, reading comprehension); (3) self-esteem & comparison with peers; and (4) protective factors (student, teacher, classmates, parents). An overview of the coded challenging situations and protective factors of students, therapists, and parents/guardians is provided in [Table 1](#).

Results

The challenging situations and protective factors were mentioned in varying numbers from the different perspectives (see [Figure 1](#)). The students reported the highest number of challenging situations in the interviews, followed by the therapists' questionnaires, while the fewest situations were identified by the parents' questionnaires. [Table 1](#) provides an overview of the frequency and distribution of coded statements per category and informant group. The subsequent section provides a more detailed description of the results from each perspective. The initial letters of the participant coding indicate the country (A = Austria, GER = Germany, CH = Switzerland), while the following letters indicate the respective perspective (PA = parents, ST = students, TH = therapists).

Negative interactions

Negative interactions with parents

Parents reported that their child did not understand a topic at school and that "[t]his led to us as a family struggling through the demands, with the atmosphere worsening steadily. The learning objective was still not achieved, and my child increasingly expressed feeling stupid and incapable" (GER2_PA, Pos. 8). The child added that, due to difficulties in understanding, they needed a lot of time to complete homework and experienced this situation as highly stressful (GER2_ST). One child perceived the additional exercises as

Table 1. Overview of the coded challenging situations and protective factors of students, therapists, and parents/guardians per student.

		neg. parents interaction	neg. class/classmates	neg. teacher interaction	working speed	pressure of grades	additional support	homework	writing	reading/verbal expression	reading comprehension	self-esteem	comparison with	protect. factors student	protect. factors teacher	protect. factor classmates	protect. factor parents	various topics
GER1	ST																	
	TH																	
	PA																	
GER2	ST																	
	TH																	
	PA																	
GER3	ST																	
	TH																	
GER4	ST																	
	TH																	
GER5	ST																	
	TH																	
GER6	ST																	
	TH																	
GER7	ST																	
	TH																	
GER8	ST																	
	TH																	
A1	ST																	
	TH																	
	PA																	
A2	ST																	
	TH																	
	PA																	
A3	ST																	
	TH																	
	PA																	
A4	ST																	
	TH																	

(Continued)

Figure 1. Number of coded segments in total, including student, parent/guardian, and therapist perspectives.

friends in the class (GER1_ST) and receiving no support from their seat neighbour (A1_ST).

Negative interactions with teachers

In interactions with teachers, several aspects were perceived negatively: a lack of understanding regarding the diagnosis, increasing academic demands, the fast pace of instruction (GER2_PA; A5_PA; A5_TH), frequent changes of teachers (A3_PA; A3_TH), and fear of (new) teachers (GER1_PA; CH2_TH). Three students reported that it was unpleasant and stressful not being able to complete the reading test, a dictation, or a text task in mathematics due to insufficient time for reading or writing, or because they had to ask for help and the teacher did not recognise their difficulties (GER2_ST; A3_ST; CH3_ST). One student shared: But I also, I'll say, got into a lot of trouble because I just didn't (.) really (.) understand it. Because it was explained to me A THOUSAND times and I STILL didn't get it when I was supposed to do something, and [the teacher said] "Why don't you just read it?" [..] (imitates teacher) (GER2_ST, Pos. 66). Another teacher, who was unaware of the diagnosis, reacted angrily when a task was not understood, which led the child to feel frustrated and angry (GER1_ST). One more child reported feeling unsupported by a teacher who did not intervene when the child was laughed at by others (GER2_ST).

Task mastery

Working speed

At school, time limits were often set – for example, for writing essays, completing assignments, or taking assessments – which students with writing difficulties were unable to meet, as they required more time (GER2_ST; A3_ST; A5_ST; CH7_ST; A3_PA; A5_PA; CH3_PA; CH4_PA; A2_TH; A3_TH; A5_TH). Students reported that other children read

(from a book) (CH2_ST; CH4_ST; A2_PA) or write (during group exercises) significantly faster (CH4_ST; CH9_PA). One child described the experience as follows: “I find it uncomfortable when we all get the same worksheet and we all have to read it. For example, in five minutes, and then I can’t read it in five minutes, and yeah”. (CH3_ST, Pos. 2). Difficulties due to slower reading and writing were also reported in foreign language classes (CH6_PA).

Pressure of grades

In Austria, pressure to achieve good grades increased as students approached the transition to secondary school at the end of fourth grade (A5_PA; A1_TH). Additional pressure arose from tests, exams, written assignments, and time constraints, as well as from teacher feedback in general (GER3_ST; CH8_ST; GER4_TH; A5_TH; CH8_TH). In some cases, students put pressure on themselves to achieve good grades (A2_TH). Some students noticed that their grades were poor (GER3_ST; CH8_ST), particularly in comparison to their classmates (GER7_ST). The prospect of having to repeat a grade was also experienced as stressful (A3_TH). One student shared: “We will soon have a test. I ALWAYS feel uncomfortable because I’m afraid I’ll make a mistake. (.) BUT actually, it’s okay to have tests, but (.) I’m just SCARED (.) that I won’t understand anything”. (CH8_ST, Pos. 50).

Additional support

Additional practice exercises at home were perceived as a form of punishment, as their purpose was not understood (CH4_PA). They were also associated with increased effort (A1_ST), and extra exercises at school were experienced as burdensome (A3_TH). One student described this: “(..) Well, sometimes I have situations where I really don’t like getting different material – even in things I’m already good at – but then I struggle, and I think to myself: why am I getting different material now?” (A5_ST, Pos. 10).

Homework

Homework was difficult to complete due to its scope, content, and the student’s abilities (GER2_PA). It required a lot of time and concentration and was often associated with frustration or lack of motivation (GER2_ST; GER4_ST; GER8_ST; A1_ST; CH4_ST; CH4_PA; A2_TH; A3_TH; A5_TH), and sometimes even with anger (CH1_TH). One student remarked: “Sometimes I just find it stupid to still have to do homework [..]” (GER8_ST, Pos. 46), and another said: “Well, you just don’t have time, that’s why. You always have to stay seated, and that gets annoying sometimes”. (GER4_ST, Pos. 70). In some cases, exercises not completed during class had to be finished at home (A2_ST).

Writing

Writing long texts or writing under time constraints posed challenges for many students due to time pressure, the application of spelling rules, or difficulties with certain letters (GER1_ST; GER2_ST; GER3_ST; GER8_ST; A1_ST; A2_ST; A3_ST; A4_ST; A5_ST; CH2_ST; CH4_ST; CH6_ST; CH7_ST; CH8_ST; GER1_PA; A4_PA; A5_PA; CH1_PA; CH6_PA; CH9_PA; GER1_TH; GER2_TH; GER3_TH; GER4_TH; GER5_TH; GER6_TH; GER7_TH; GER8_TH; A2_TH; CH4_TH). One student handed in a blank sheet during a class test because reading the

instructions alone triggered a refusal to work (GER4_TH). The large number of mistakes led to frustration and diminished self-esteem (GER3_TH), with one student perceiving themselves as inadequate (GER2_TH) and showing little motivation to write (CH1_TH). One student expressed: “I just don’t feel comfortable writing yet” (CH7_ST, Pos. 46). The difficulties with writing were described as follows:

When it comes to writing, I often mix up uppercase and lowercase letters. And we often have copy texts, and I do copy them, but sometimes I don’t look closely at how the word is spelled, and then I write it a bit wrong. (GER3_ST, Pos. 16)

Reading/verbal expression

Reading aloud in front of the class or a large group of peers was perceived as stressful from all three perspectives – students, parents, and therapists – due to classmates making fun of the student, time pressure, or slow and error-prone reading (GER1_ST; GER2_ST; GER3_ST; GER7_ST; A3_ST; CH3_ST; CH2_ST; CH5_ST; CH8_ST; GER1_PA; A2_PA; A3_PA; A5_PA; CH1_PA; CH3_PA; CH_PA; CH8_PA; GER2_TH; GER5_TH; GER8_TH; CH2_TH; CH3_TH; CH4_TH; CH5_TH). One child described their reading difficulties as follows:

When I read aloud, I noticed that I sometimes skip a few words. Or that I skip letters because I always read way too fast. But when I read quietly to myself, then I always read slowly so I can understand all the letters. (CH8_ST, Pos. 6)

Reading comprehension

Difficulties in reading comprehension became apparent particularly during assessments, learning stations, reading comprehension tasks, and time-limited exercises, as students struggled to grasp content quickly and found reading for meaning challenging (GER1_ST; GER2_ST; GER3_ST; GER4_ST; GER7_ST; A2_ST; A4_ST; A5_ST; CH2_ST; CH3_ST; CH4_ST; CH5_ST; CH6_ST; CH9_ST; A3_PA; CH6_PA; GER1_TH; GER3_TH; GER4_TH; GER5_TH; GER6_TH; GER7_TH; A2_TH; CH4_TH; CH5_TH; CH9_TH). These difficulties were especially pronounced at the word level (GER8_ST; CH8_ST; GER2_TH; GER8_TH). One student described their experience as follows:

We once had these reading (.) tests that we did quite often. (.) I just didn’t participate at all/(.) I couldn’t keep up in that time. (.) I just skimmed the sentences and then we had to, um, tick the correct ones. But I usually got them wrong because I hadn’t really read the sentences properly. (GER2_ST, Pos. 46)

Another student said: “At home I always read like that, but I always had this kind of block when it came to reading”. (CH9_ST, Pos. 6). Reading was described as exhausting (CH6_ST). Two students only became aware of their difficulties after others pointed them out (GER1_ST; GER6_TH) or as school demands increased. Reading comprehension difficulties were also noticeable in other subjects, such as mathematics (CH3_ST; A2_PA; CH5_PA; CH2_TH; CH5_TH). Similar issues arose in subjects like science, “Human & Environment”, or “Nature, Human & Society”, where students struggled to understand the instructions (A5_TH; CH2_TH; CH5_TH).

Self-esteem

Self-esteem was the only category that was mentioned more frequently by parents and professionals than by the students themselves. Reading unfamiliar texts at school, completing written tasks or tests, and the awareness of their own difficulties often led students to feel stressed, frustrated, overwhelmed or uncomfortable. This sometimes resulted in withdrawal, refusal to read, fear of failure, and reduced self-esteem (GER3_ST; CH3_ST; CH7_ST; CH8_PA; GER3_TH; GER5_TH; A3_TH; CH8_TH). A discrepancy between the student's self-perception – believing their performance had improved – and the teacher's negative evaluation led to demotivation and self-doubt (A5_PA). In other cases, students did not understand the cause of their difficulties, which led to refusal to engage (GER1_TH). Negative feedback from teachers made students more aware of their struggles and failures, resulting in defensive or avoidant behaviour when they felt overwhelmed (GER4_TH). One student, for example, perceived themselves as "stupid" and incapable of learning due to not achieving the expected learning goals (GER2_PA).

Comparison with classmates

Students compared their performance with that of their peers and noticed that they read more slowly and made more mistakes, as they needed more time to read and understand tasks (A5_ST; CH3_ST; CH4_ST; A2_PA; A3_PA; CH4_PA; CH1_TH; CH4_TH). One student described the situation as follows: "I actually always struggled a lot more and just couldn't keep up with the others". (A5_ST, Pos. 4).

Protective factors

Students

Students are aware of their own difficulties (GER2_ST; GER8_TH; CH1_TH), but also recognise their own progress, describing reading and writing as becoming easier (GER1_ST; GER2_ST; GER5_ST; A4_ST; CH4_ST; CH6_ST). One student demonstrated a determined and ambitious personality (GER8_TH; GER8_ST), while another appeared curious and eager to learn (CH6_TH). School is not perceived as a burden, students consciously left school and its challenges behind, looking forward to leisure activities and time with friends (A1_ST; A2_ST; A3_ST; A4_ST; A5_ST; CH4_ST; CH6_ST; CH7_ST; CH8_ST; CH9_ST). In class, there is a respectful and supportive atmosphere where students do not laugh at each other (GER8_ST). Classmates were perceived as sources of support (GER4_ST; CH2_ST). One child described how they deal with mistakes as follows:

Well, at first just normally, because I didn't know that it was anything unusual to make so many mistakes. Because others also make a lot of mistakes. Of course, there are some in my class who are really good. (GER8_ST, Pos. 10)

When asked why they do not focus on their reading or writing difficulties, another student responded: "Because it's not important. I should focus on myself". (CH8_ST, Pos. 46).

Another student relied on a positive self-concept, stating: “I just thought I could do it, and then I kept going”. (CH2_ST, Pos. 10).

Teachers

The teacher or another learning support staff member served for some as a trusted point of contact (GER1_ST; GER3_ST; GER4_ST; GER7_ST; A2_ST; CH2_ST; CH6_ST; CH7_ST; CH9_PA). Support included reading out instructions, not giving a reading grade, allowing extra time (GER7_TH), reading aloud one-on-one with the teacher or working directly with them (A4_ST; CH3_ST; CH3_TH), allowing the child to ask peers for help during class (GER4_ST; GER5_ST), or suggesting dyslexia therapy (GER4_ST). The teacher’s support and understanding were frequently emphasised: “Then I often go to the teachers and say that something is bothering me, and they usually find a solution for it”. (GER3_ST, Pos. 60) or “I often raise my hand, or I ask her if (.) she could help me quickly (.), and then she helps me and (.) sometimes gives me, um (4) um/support strategies that (.) help me make better progress”. (A5_ST, Pos. 14). In a private school, teaching was individualised (CH6_PA), and some schools used mixed-age learning groups with weekly plans (GER6_ST; GER5_TH; GER6_TH).

Classmates

Some students were accepted by their classmates (GER2_ST; GER6_ST; CH6_ST; CH5_PA), which is attributed to the small class size and the classmates’ awareness of the situation (CH2_PA), or to the generally heterogeneous nature of the class (CH2_ST; CH9_TH). In addition, some students received support from others (GER5_ST; GER6_ST; GER6_TH A2_ST; CH2_ST; CH7_ST; CH1_TH). One student mentioned that they enjoy reading in tandem with a friend (A3_ST).

Parents

Parents supported their child with homework (CH7_ST; A3_TH), practised together with them (CH8_ST), and advocated for their child to repeat a grade in order to further improve their performance (GER3_ST). One child added that the parents bought a book where they could focus solely on reading, as the illustrations were not distracting (CH9_ST).

Discussion

This study examined challenging school-related situations and protective factors for students with dyslexia from the perspectives of students, parents/guardians, and dyslexia or speech-language therapists across three European countries. A central aim was to compare these perspectives to identify convergences and discrepancies and to underline the importance of adopting a multiperspective approach to better understand and support children with dyslexia in school contexts.

Convergences and discrepancies across perspectives

The results show clear convergences between the perspectives of students, parents/guardians, and therapists in several areas, such as the burden associated with time pressure during tasks, negative classroom experiences (for example, reading aloud), and emotional consequences like frustration, stress, or fear of failure. Students, parents/guardians, and therapists alike highlight the connection between dyslexia and socio-emotional vulnerabilities by reporting how situations such as classroom reading, standardised assessments, and unaccommodated academic expectations contributed to high emotional distress (see also Alexander-Passe, 2006; Hellendoorn & Ruijsenaars, 2000; McNulty, 2003).

However, some discrepancies emerged. Notably, self-esteem issues were more frequently addressed by parents and therapists than by the students themselves. While students described feelings of discomfort, demotivation, and frustration, these were not always explicitly linked to self-worth. This may reflect students' limited metacognitive or emotional reflection abilities at this developmental stage (Perry et al., 2002). In line with this, some students only became aware of their learning difficulties through social interactions – such as noticing peer reactions or receiving negative feedback from teachers (Deacon et al., 2020; Wilmot et al., 2023) – suggesting that awareness of one's own challenges often emerges from external cues rather than internal reflection.

Implications for research, educational, and educational psychology, practice

The inclusion of multiple perspectives seems essential in capturing the complex interplay between cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions of dyslexia. Relying on a single source of information (for example, only student self-report or therapist observation) risks overlooking key aspects of a child's experience (Huber et al., 2019). For instance, while therapists reported the need for additional time and students' emotional strain during assessments, students often described their experience in behavioural terms (for example, avoidance, rushing, or giving up), and parents emphasised home-based tensions such as arguments around homework. Adopting a multiperspective framework, as proposed by the international classification of functioning, disability, and health (children & youth version; WHO, 2007), acknowledges that functioning and disability result from the dynamic interaction between individuals and their environment. By triangulating insights from students, caregivers, and professionals, this study contributes to a more ecological understanding of the everyday challenges and resources available to children with dyslexia (Al-Yagon, 2016; Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006).

The study underscores how school-related stressors can have far-reaching effects on the psycho-social development of children with dyslexia. Recurrent failure experiences, negative social comparisons, and teacher misunderstandings not only hinder academic engagement but also increase the risk of reduced self-worth and learned helplessness (Fotini et al., 2025). As shown in prior research, these dynamics may contribute to long-term withdrawal, anxiety, or depression (Terras et al., 2009). To prevent these downstream consequences, early and sustained support systems are crucial. This includes not only formal therapeutic interventions but also emotionally responsive classroom environments where

reading and writing difficulties are destigmatised, and individual learning progress is valued. Teacher education programmes must foster greater awareness of the emotional impact of dyslexia and promote strategies for differentiated instruction (Snowling & Hulme, 2012).

Educational and school psychologists, working alongside dyslexia specialists or speech and language therapists, students, parents and schools, are ideally placed to support a better understanding of the complexities of challenges and protective factors evident within the social and academic school curriculum for children and young people (CYP) with dyslexia. Findings from this current study might be used to inform such practice, as well as assisting the development of future research in other national or international contexts to better understand how these issues are similar to, or contrast with, the current situation in the three European countries represented in this research.

Strengths, limitations, and future directions

A major strength of this study lies in its inclusion of first-person narratives from students with dyslexia, who remain underrepresented in the literature (Nalavany et al., 2011). The triangulation of student, parent, and therapist perspectives enhances the credibility of the findings and allows for a more nuanced interpretation. At the same time, the retrospective nature of some parent and therapist reports may be subject to recall bias. Additionally, as the study involved children already receiving therapy, the sample may not be representative of all students with dyslexia, particularly those without access to support services. This limits the credibility of findings to dyslexic students not receiving therapy.

Future research should explore how different support systems interact across school, home, and therapy settings and examine which types of support (emotional, instructional, structural) are most effective from each perspective. In addition, more nuanced approaches to capturing children's self-perception and awareness of their difficulties should be developed, recognising that children's verbalisations of challenges may lag behind their emotional experiences. Furthermore, including the classroom teachers' perspective in the triangulation would be valuable, allowing for a more detailed analyses of convergences and discrepancies across perspectives.

Conclusion

While many difficulties were commonly identified across perspectives, key discrepancies, particularly in the awareness and articulation of emotional strain, underscore the importance of viewing dyslexia not solely as an individual learning disorder but as a condition shaped through social interaction and context. Recognising the interplay between academic demands and socio-emotional experiences is critical for designing responsive, inclusive, and individualised support strategies. A multiperspective approach, rooted in close collaboration among students, families, and professionals, is essential for mitigating psycho-social risks and fostering well-being in learners with dyslexia.

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Data availability statement

The participants of this study did not provide written consent for their data to be shared publicly. Therefore, due to the sensitive nature of the research, the supporting data are not available.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Interview guide (students' perspective)

Start

Therapist: "I want to talk to you about school today. I record our conversations so you can talk and we don't have to write anything down. When did you realise that you were having trouble reading or writing something?"

During school (lessons)

"Now imagine you are sitting in school and lessons have started. Are there certain situations that are particularly unpleasant/stressful/difficult for you? What are they?"

[If the child does not understand, explain it further].

"For example, there may be certain situations that are particularly stressful for you during lessons, that make you sad or angry. There may also be situations that you find particularly difficult. These are situations that make you feel uncomfortable at school".

[Ask if the child only mentions situations from one area (tasks, interaction with classmates, interaction with the teacher). Ask once again for each of the two missing settings]

"What is particularly difficult for you in class? What does the teacher do? What do the other children do?"

After school

"Imagine that school is now over and you can go home. Is there anything from school that is still unpleasant for you afterwards? What is it?"

[Give further information, if the child doesn't say much]

"For example, are there certain tasks or situations that you have experienced or that are still pending and that are still unpleasant/stressful/difficult for you after school? Which tasks/situations are these?"

[Ask if only reading/writing is mentioned]

"What exactly is unpleasant/stressful/difficult for you? When/when is it particularly unpleasant/stressful/difficult for you?"

Conclusion of the conversation

"So now we've talked a lot about school. What are you looking forward to after school?"

Appendix B. Overview of participating students

Country and Codes	Perspectives	Code of therapist	Age years; months	Gender	School grade	Years of school attendance	Diagnosis/reading/spelling ¹	Further diagnosis ²	Duration from diagnosis to start of treatment	Duration of the treatment at the time of the interview in months
GER1	ST, TH, PA	1	11;2	m	4	5	Standard. tests	Social-emotional disorder	6	24
GER2	ST, TH, PA	1	11;0	f	4	5	F81.3	dyscalculia, SES	6	24
GER3	ST, TH	1	10;6	m	4	5	F81.0	SES, ADHD	3	18
GER4	ST, TH	1	10;1	f	4	4	F81.0	dyscalculia, social-emotional disorder	6	10
GER5	ST, TH	1	9;4	f	3	4	F81.3	dyscalculia, SES, Depressive Episode	4	14
GER6	ST, TH	1	9;2	f	2	3	F81.3	dyscalculia	6	6
GER7	ST, TH	1	9;7	f	4	4	F81.0	SES	3	0
GER8	ST, TH	1	10;3	f	4	4	F81.0	-	4	0
A1	ST, TH, PA	2	9;0	m	4	4	Standard. tests	-	2	4
A2	ST, TH, PA	3	9;10	f	4	4	F81.0	-	4	4
A3	ST, TH, PA	3	8;8	m	3	3	F81.0	-	1	7
A4	ST, TH	3	10;1	m	4	4	Standard. tests	SES	0	18
A5	ST, TH, PA	3	11;5	f	4	4	Standard. tests	dyscalculia	6	17
CH1	TH, PA	4	9;4	m	3	3	F81.1	dyscalculia	0	9
CH2	ST, TH, PA	5	10;0	f	4	6	Specific reading disorder	-	n.a.	30
CH3	ST, TH, PA	6	11;9	m	5	6	F81.0	-	1	51
CH4	ST, TH, PA	6	10;8	m	4	4	F81.0	ADHD, dyscalculia	3	19
CH5	ST, TH, PA	6	8;11	m	3	3	F81.0	-	1	1
CH6	ST, TH, PA	7	9;11	m	4	5,5	F81.0	-	4	4
CH7	ST, TH, PA	7	11;2	m	4	6	F81.0	ADHD	n.a.	65

(Continued)

Country and Codes	Perspectives	Code of therapist	Age years; months	Gender	School grade	Years of school attendance	Diagnosis reading/spelling ¹	Futher diagnosis ²	Duration from diagnosis to start of treatment	Duration of the treatment at the time of the interview in months
CH8	ST, TH, PA	8	11;4	f	4	4,5	F81.0	-	n.a.	47
CH9	ST, TH, PA	9	10;0	f	4	4	F81.0	-	n.a.	19

Notes: student = perspective of student, PA = perspective of parents, TH = perspective of therapist, ¹diagnosis (ICD 10): F81.0 reading and spelling disorder, F81.1 specific spelling disorder, F81.3 Mixed disorder of scholastic skills; ²SES = Specific developmental disorders of speech and language, ADHD = attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.